

NATURANCE

Nature for insurance,
insurance for nature

Milestone 5.3 Online citizen forum II launched

Authors: Agnese Glauda, Soraya Melinato, Davide Michielin, Andrea Staccione (CMCC - Euro-Mediterranean Centre on Climate Change)

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1. Executive Summary

The report presents the outcomes of the second online citizen engagement forum, held by the NATURANCE consortium as part of the project's *Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results*, under the initiative called [Naturethon](#). The initiative aimed to organize citizen group meetings throughout Europe and beyond, focused on identifying innovative financial strategies for Nature-based Solutions (NbS) in the context of climate action and disaster risk mitigation. Naturethon targets a diverse range of participants, including students from various backgrounds, young professionals, local administrators, and representatives of environmental NGOs. The initiative was led by CMCC, with contributions from ICLEI Europe, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology and Stockholm University.

The second edition, titled "[Citizens Growing Nature-Based Futures](#)", ran from **5 September to 8 December 2025**. To respond to the interest shown by individuals without local groups during the first edition, the 2025 open call allowed **individual registration** through a statement of interest to form new groups. Online collaborative boards were introduced to guide participants more effectively as they developed their projects during each hands-on webinar. Once completed, the boards were compiled into a **logbook**, which served as the foundation for the final submission. In terms of outcomes, 19 groups successfully completed the interactive process and submitted their projects for final evaluation. Altogether, **103 people actively participated** in this edition by submitting a final project. The proposals covered a wide variety of topics, ranging from flood risk to wildfires, biodiversity loss, and habitat degradation, and came from 14 countries. The [preliminary results were presented](#) at the Italian National Conference on Science Communication in Trieste on 2 December 2025. The event was attended by over 400 participants.

The second edition was preceded by the first forum, titled "[Navigating new paths for NbS Finance](#)", which ran from June to September 2024. Its outcomes are reported in detail in [Deliverable D5.3](#) (M30). A series of five in-person and online events, titled "[Naturethon+](#)", was organised to engage specific stakeholders between the two calls (December 2024-August 2025). As of January 2026, the entire Naturethon initiative has engaged **435 participants from 76 groups**, approaching the KPI of 500 stated in the grant agreement.

Since a few activities are still ongoing, the target is expected to be reached and surpassed by the end of the project.

2. Background

Mobilizing public and citizen engagement is essential for inclusive practices toward social change, fostering a sense of empowerment and creating conditions of full transparency, accountability, and trust. [The Council Recommendation on a Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe](#) calls for a more active citizens and societal engagement in research and innovation to be promoted in all its dimensions, to raise awareness of the benefits and impact of research and innovation in people's daily lives, ensure a greater diversity of approaches for designing and implementing research and innovation policy and make them more relevant for society.

However, citizen engagement for impactful knowledge valorisation presents both opportunities and challenges due to the multifaceted needs and competencies of the actors involved. These may include universities, research organisations, Small and Medium sized Enterprises (SMEs), local communities and municipalities, non-governmental organisations, citizens groups, social partners, and arts and cultural institutions.

In order to effectively implement the initiative, the WP5 designed the Naturethon framework taking into account the [Code of Practice on citizen engagement for knowledge valorisation](#), recommended by the European Commission. The Code offers practical guidance to strengthen links between research entities and societal actors for better uptake of research results. It identifies the need for a strategic approach at the organisation level, which encourages cross-sector collaboration, awareness raising, and strengthening the role of intermediaries. It also proposes the use of incentives, co-creation tools and digital solutions with a human-centric and sustainable design. Moreover, the Code facilitates the creation of an **enabling environment** and participatory processes and practices of sustainable citizen engagement for improved knowledge valorisation.

The Code urges organizations to develop an **engagement strategy** with clear impact pathways and roadmaps to ensure value creation for the economy and society. It promotes synergies, capacity building, and skills development in participatory processes, as well as

cross-domain collaboration, sound intellectual asset management, recognition of citizens' contributions, and open science practices. To ensure **social inclusion**, diversity, and gender equality, the Code emphasizes equal engagement of all target groups, removal of participation barriers, and the involvement of relevant professional skills. It also provides guidance on **scaling and replicating** citizen engagement actions through toolkits, guidelines, platforms, intermediaries, and **awareness-raising** initiatives, and calls for **recognition of engagement efforts** through incentives, rewards, prizes, and other schemes. Finally, it outlines recommendations for **assessing the effectiveness** of citizen engagement and participatory processes for knowledge valorisation, including key areas, indicators, and metrics for an evaluation framework.

Regarding the challenges, the policy brief "[Citizens' awareness of EU missions and opportunities for citizen engagement](#)" summarises the biggest barriers to participation in citizen engagement initiatives. Lack of awareness and lack of trust in public institutions were the most commonly cited barriers to citizen participation. Lack of interest or not having enough time are, in most cases, seen as the least significant barriers. Another barrier encountered involves expanding the initiative network beyond that of the project experts and highly skilled professionals.

3. Definitions

According to the Commission Recommendation (EU) 2024/736 of 1 March 2024 on a [Code of Practice on citizen engagement for knowledge valorisation](#).

- **CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT:** involvement of citizens in participatory processes of decision making, implementation and monitoring, to improve quality, transparency and ownership of policies at local, national and EU level, which has been strongly supported by the Conference for the Future of Europe and the resulting European Citizens Panels for addressing current and future challenges and adapting new tools through citizens' panels in key areas.
- **CITIZEN SCIENCE:** voluntary participation of non-professional scientists in research and innovation (R&I) at different stages and at different levels of engagement, from

shaping research agendas and policies, to gathering, processing and analysing data, and assessing the outcomes of research.

- **KNOWLEDGE VALORISATION:** process of creating social and economic value from knowledge by linking different areas and sectors and by transforming data, know-how and research results into sustainable products, services, solutions and knowledge-based policies that benefit society.

4. Second edition

4.1 Overview

Naturethon facilitated the creation of citizen groups focused on discussing Nature-based Solutions (NbS) and their applicability to disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation within local communities. Participants developed specific knowledge and skills through virtual participation in recurring, hands-on webinars, complemented by individual online follow-up exchanges and tailored guidance. In addition, participants had access to a continuously updated [Digital Library](#), as well as a periodic newsletter—featuring articles, podcasts, videos, reports, and inspiring stories—that helped maintain citizen engagement throughout the process. Group participants were guided step by step by the Naturethon team in designing their own projects through online collaborative boards. At the conclusion of the process, all submissions were evaluated by experts based on their innovation, feasibility, and environmental and social impacts.

4.2 Target Audiences

The Naturethon initiative targets a diverse range of participants, including students from various backgrounds, young professionals, local administrators, and representatives of environmental NGOs. More broadly, it engages citizens who are interested in adaptation issues in their local communities and who enjoy participating in meaningful dialogue and exchanging ideas. Intended group size varies from a minimum of 3 and a maximum of 10 people, varied in age, gender, and citizenship.

4.3 Timeline

As suggested by the review conducted by experts from the [European Citizen Science Association](#) (ECSA) during the first Naturethon open call, the second edition of the initiative – originally scheduled for January to March 2026 – was brought forward to autumn 2025 to better align with school and academic calendars. Titled “**Citizens Growing Nature-Based Futures**”, the second Naturethon open call was announced on the project website on [5 September 2025](#), with the official launch taking place during the first webinar on [9 October](#). The program comprised two other hands-on webinars ([28 October](#) and [26 November](#)), each followed by a one-hour interactive session, as well as a catch-up session on 2 December reserved for groups intending to submit proposals. The initiative ran until **8 December 2025**. The three winning teams were announced on [18 December](#).

4.4 Recruitment

The second open call of the Naturethon was widely promoted through external newsletters and/or platforms of relevant Knowledge Networks such as [MIP4Adapt](#) and [Climate ADAPT](#), [NBS Italy Hub](#), several HE projects and clusters of projects, international and national institutions such as the [UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction](#) and the [Italian Ministry of Education](#). As with the first Naturethon open call, the initial step of the second edition involved **registering a group** through an EUSurvey form. This ensured that at least one representative of each group - colloquially referred to as the “*Naturethon Champion (NC)*” - would receive updates, resources, and support throughout the citizen engagement process. NCs were invited to coordinate the activities of the group and recruit participants. To respond to the interest shown by individuals without already formed local groups during the first open call, the 2025 edition allowed **individual registration** through a statement of interest to form new groups. As a result, 28 participants were supported by the Naturethon team in forming 5 additional groups.

4.5 Structure

During the second edition, the structure of the first Naturethon initiative was revised to provide additional support to the participating groups while ensuring a bottom-up dialogue within the groups and their broader communities. To this end, three hands-on webinars and

an additional catch-up session were organized. Details on topics and speakers are provided in the [Webinars](#) section (4.7). Each webinar was structured in two parts. In the first one, high-level speakers delivered presentations on relevant topics using a pragmatic approach. In the second part, group participants were guided step by step by the Naturethon team in designing their own projects through online collaborative boards.

The team of facilitators and experts was available to answer questions and provide further insights, creating in-depth worksheets for the groups. The guided exercise process involved four steps: identifying challenges, generating nature-based ideas, mapping stakeholders, and developing financial strategies. Progress from each session was documented in a logbook, which then served as the foundation for the final submission.

CHALLENGES	
CLIMATE	<p>Primary Challenge: Intensified heat waves, prolonged drought, UHI effects, and air quality stress.</p> <p>Associated challenges: Public health risk, heat stress, and reduced thermal comfort for vulnerable groups such as elderly, patients, children, outdoor workers, travellers and low income households etc..</p>
ENVIRONMENTAL	<p>Primary Challenge: low green space ratio especially low tree canopy coverage, fragmented green area, impermeable pavement (asphalt, concrete with low albedo), limited and polluted water bodies.</p> <p>Associated challenges: urban heat island effect (UHI), heat stress, loss of access for cooling, poor air quality, community disconnection, compounding crises. Competing land-use priorities between housing, green spaces, and mobility.</p>
SOCIAL	<p>Primary Challenge: Vulnerable groups are exposed to heat waves, unequal access to cooling infrastructure, Public space exposure. Stress of healthcare cost for public sector and individuals. Low engagement of private sectors and citizens on NbS implementation.</p> <p>Associated challenges: Higher health risk, social inequity, limited adaptive capacity and community resilience, energy poverty, social exclusion, reduced social interaction.</p>
ECONOMIC	<p>Primary Challenge: Escalating energy consumption and cost for cooling, higher healthcare cost, business activity disruption, lower productivity, higher heritage preservation cost, increased insurance cost, tourism economy impacted. Heavy financial expenditure for municipality on heat waves adaptation and NbS implementation. Lack of effective financing mechanism and operational approach for NbS scale-up.</p> <p>Associated challenges: rising electricity bills, healthcare costs both for individuals, households pay more for insurance premium or cannot afford insurance premium, municipal stress for healthcare, reduced local tourism business revenue, small business vulnerability, community frustration, job insecurity.</p>
NbS elements to implement to address the challenges identified	
<p>NbS IDEAS</p>	
GOVERNANCE	<p>Potential NbS: Integrating NbS into municipal urban planning. Provide incentive and regulations NbS projects. Coordinated action across municipalities, metropolitan authorities, and regional agencies. Linking NbS governance with health policy to protect vulnerable groups and to get access to healthcare budget. Deploying AI and GIS tools to track NbS effectiveness. Creating evaluation metrics for environmental, social, and economic co-benefits. Foster public participation. Scale up NbS projects. Associated NbS elements: Embed NbS into municipal building codes. Use heat vulnerability maps to prioritize NbS in areas with <15% green coverage. Ensure every district benefits from cooling interventions. Guarantee equitable distribution across Milan's municipi.</p>

Figure 2 – Logbook of one of the submitted proposals.

Additionally, the initiative’s [Digital Library](#) – comprising inspiring stories, case studies, podcasts, and recordings of the webinars – was further expanded to provide practical insights into the successful implementation of NbS across diverse contexts and communities. This platform served both as a source of inspiration and as a reference point for best practices. Finally, [a series of 7 newsletters](#) – including articles, videos, reports, and inspiring stories – was sent to sustain participant engagement throughout the process.

At the conclusion of the process, all submissions were evaluated by experts based on their innovation, feasibility, and environmental and social impacts. Although the logbook format was recommended, submissions were accepted in a variety of formats, including drawings, written texts, and videos.

4.6 Events

To enhance engagement, the second edition of the initiative included three hands-on webinars and a catch-up session.

Date	Title	Co-organisers	Speakers	Attendees
09.10.25	Seeds of Change: Citizens Growing Nature-Based Futures	EUCLIPA	Andrea Staccione (CMCC), Luciana Favaro (EUCLIPA)	33
28.10.25	Innovative Tools for Success Stories	ARCADIA , NBS EduWorld	Marcelo Gerlach (ICLEI Europe), Nicolas Keller (Växtverket), Ludwig Wahlund Sonesson (City of Malmö)	41
26.11.25	Financing local NbS for lasting resilience	Land4Climate	Lenka Slavikova (UJEP), Jaroslav Mysiak (CMCC)	50
02.12.25	Extra-training session	-	-	10

4.6.1 Webinar 1

On October 9, the hands-on webinar “[Seeds of Change](#)” kicked-off the second open call of the initiative. Luciana Favaro, the president of the [Italian network of European Climate Pact Ambassadors \(EuCliPa\)](#), highlighted the importance of citizen engagement in climate adaptation measures within a European framework, sharing insights and best practices. Andrea Staccione, from CMCC, offered a deep dive into NbS, explaining what they are, their benefits, and how they are applied in practice. The event concluded with a collaborative work session, where **33 participants** actively engaged in developing their own ideas and solutions.

4.6.2 Webinar 2

The second hands-on webinar, titled “[*Innovative Tools for Success Stories*](#)” took place on 28 October and was co-organised with the Horizon Europe project [ARCADIA](#), part of the **NBS4EU** cluster. Marcelo Gerlach from ICLEI Europe introduced the *Youth Inclusion Toolkit for Local Authorities*, developed through a co-creative process within the [NBS EduWorld](#) project. Following this, Nicolas Keller, Sustainability Educator at **Växtverket NGO**, and Ludwig Wahlund Sonesson, Project Manager at the **City of Malmö**, illustrated how the City of Malmö, Sweden, orchestrated a network of local associations to engage diverse citizen groups in the development of urban NbS, with a focus on community and sustainability. The event concluded with an interactive workshop. **41 participants** began co-developing NbS ideas tailored to their own local contexts, setting the stage for future collaboration and innovation.

4.6.3 Webinar 3

The third hands-on webinar, titled “[Financing local NbS for lasting resilience](#)” took place on **26 November** and was co-organised with the HE project [Land4Climate](#), part of the **NBS4EU** cluster. Lenka Slavíková (UJEP) presented the NbS Alternative Financing Guide, an interactive resource designed specifically for practitioners who are aiming to deploy NbS solutions in their communities. Jaroslav Mysiak, CMCC and NATURANCE project coordinator, presented some of the project’s outcomes, highlighting financial tools that promote a local, collaborative, ecosystem-based approach to increase community resilience and preparedness. During the interactive session, **50 participants** discussed financial strategies and key actors and stakeholders to support their NbS proposals, exchange ideas, foster collaboration and finalise their proposal for real-world impact

4.6.4 Extra-training session

The extra-training session took place on **2 December** and aimed to provide additional, tailored support to the groups participating in the Naturethon. The session was designed to be highly interactive, starting with an overview of the initiative and the tasks proposed in the logbook as guidance. This was followed by a detailed walkthrough of the submission form and an extended Q&A session to discuss participants' ideas. 10 people took part, representing several groups. The discussion focused on their proposals to jointly explore potential directions and further development, with particular attention to identifying key stakeholders to involve and financing strategies to support the development of their projects.

4.7 Rewards

As experienced by previous similar initiatives, participation is often driven by specific incentives. While monetary prizes are often seen as the most effective incentive to engagement, this initiative has opted for knowledge recognition and access to an expert network as participation rewards. This could be considered as a less motivating incentive, but it also guarantees the selection of highly motivated participants. To recognize the participants' effort, all members of each group received a Certificate of Participation, while representatives of the winning groups were invited to the award ceremony at the [Finance Innovation Festival](#), hosted by the Naturance Consortium from 3–5 February 2026 in Brussels, where they will showcase their projects. In honour of each awarded group, a tree was planted in the [Naturethon forest](#) in partnership with [Treedom](#), creating a living legacy that reflects the impact of their ideas. In addition, all members of the awarded groups received a NATURANCE water bottle.

5. Results

5.1 Participation

The second open call of the Naturethon generated significant interest among participants. Overall, 16 local groups registered to take part. Registration by individual participants led to the formation and active support of 5 additional international groups with a shared interest

in specific hazards, bringing the total number of participating groups to 21. Among these, **19 groups** successfully completed the interactive process and submitted their projects for final evaluation, nearly doubling the number of projects submitted in the first edition (10).

The proposals covered a wide variety of topics, ranging from flood risk to wildfires, biodiversity loss, and habitat degradation, and came from 14 countries across Africa (Ethiopia, Ghana, Malawi, Mauritania, Nigeria, and South Africa), Asia (Jordan, India, Pakistan, and the Philippines), and Europe (Italy, Georgia, Portugal, and Romania). Altogether, **103 people** actively participated in this edition by submitting a final project, in line with participation in the first open call (116). The [preliminary results of the Naturethon were presented](#) at the Italian **National Conference on Science Communication** in Trieste on 2 December. Organized by the International School for Advanced Studies (SISSA), this 4-day conference is a key national forum for institutions, science communication researchers, and practitioners, driving innovation in the field. The event was attended by over 400 participants. The final results will be also shared at the NATURANCE [Finance Innovation Festival - “Insurance and Investment Opportunities for Nature-Based Transformations”](#) during a session on 5 February 2026 dedicated to Cities and Citizens. Representatives from each of the winning Naturethon teams will join the event for special recognition of their proposals, which is a unique opportunity to highlight place-based NbS interventions to a professional audience and receive feedback on their ideas.

5.2 Awarded proposals

The 19 proposals submitted were of consistently high quality. The Naturethon committee, including six experts with different backgrounds (urban planners, environmental scientists, economists, and communicators) determined that the following proposals were especially noteworthy based on the evaluation criteria: innovation, feasibility and social and environmental impact.

“Explore Sustainable Financing Strategies to Scale Up Nature-based Solutions for Cool Milan”, submitted by the *COOL MILAN* team. The project offers a clear and well-structured, data-driven analysis of urban heat waves in Milan, Italy, effectively describing the geographic context, climate risks, and impacts on vulnerable populations. The portfolio of NbS, developed around the 3-30-300 approach, is ambitious and thoughtfully designed, with interventions clearly explained and illustrated through

compelling “before and after” narratives. A major strength of the proposal lies in its innovative and comprehensive discussion of financing options, which successfully combines existing mechanisms with new instruments tailored to both the Milan context and NbS implementation. Stakeholders are well identified, and the project demonstrates a strong level of engagement and commitment. Overall, the proposal is coherent, innovative, and well aligned with the case study. The main areas for improvement concern feasibility, as the scale and number of proposed interventions would require substantial coordination among multiple actors and strong political support, as well as greater clarity in distinguishing NbS from governance and coordination measures.

Johannesburg’s Biodiversity Restoration submitted by the *Green City Champions* team. The proposal is focused on Johannesburg, South Africa, which faces biodiversity loss, habitat fragmentation, climate risks, and social challenges like food insecurity and limited green spaces. Green City Champions proposes a community-led, nature-based approach combining vertical farming, urban greening, and habitat restoration. The project empowers residents to manage farms and restore ecosystems, creating green jobs and building climate resilience. Stakeholders include local communities, municipal departments, NGOs, private investors, and research institutions. Economic sustainability relies on a mix of public and private funding, community reinvestment, and grassroots initiatives like crowdfunding and community-supported agriculture. The proposal is well structured and clearly presents the region’s main challenges, highlighting disconnections across communities, ecosystems, and policies. Its community farming and urban NbS are well designed, backed by a strong business model with good scalability potential. Stakeholder engagement and financing strategies are appropriate, and the project shows high innovation and commitment. Improvements could include clearer geographical context, stronger links between biodiversity loss and solutions, more coherence among NbS concepts, and a more focused selection of financing strategies to enhance feasibility and clarity.

C.A.R.E. – Community Action for River Ecosystems, submitted by the *RisorGivers* team, representing the environmental NGO Legambiente Treviso. The proposal tackles the degradation of spring-water ecosystems in Treviso, Italy, threatened by urbanisation, concrete encroachment, and invasive species – especially in the Montello hill–Sile river corridor. The team implemented NbS such as ecological corridors, renaturalized spring heads, peri-urban reforestation, and urban “Pocket Parks” to enhance biodiversity, recharge

aquifers, and mitigate heat islands. The initiative engages over 1,500 citizens, schools, universities, local authorities, and farmers, and relies on a hybrid financing model combining community fundraising, private partnerships, grants, and EU funding to scale up and enhance ecosystem services. The project effectively addresses biodiversity loss and environmental degradation in a high-value ecological area, combining environmental solutions with strong citizen engagement. Its governance and financial strategies support piloting, scaling, and long-term viability, while the NbS are well-documented and feasible. The financial approach is robust, although it relies mainly on public funding and donations. In the end, the project is solid, credible, and impact-oriented, with room for improvement in geographic focus and stakeholder details, and innovation depending on future implementation.

6. Outlook

As of January 2026, the entire Naturethon initiative has engaged **435 participants from 76 groups**, approaching the KPI of 500 stated in the grant agreement.

Since the activities of the [PAESC Summer School](#) – a joint initiative with the Italian National Institute for Documentation, Innovation, and Educational Research (INDIRE) and the Italian coordination of European Climate Pact Ambassadors ([EuCliPa.IT](#)), as part of the Naturethon+ series – are still ongoing, **the target is expected to be reached** and even surpassed by the end of the project.

Focused on Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans (SECAP/PAESC), this five-day training and capacity development course (25–29 August 2025), attended by 29 high-school teachers, comprised a total of 28 hours: 13 hours of online training, 10 hours of individual work, and 5 hours dedicated to final project design. NATURANCE researchers contributed to the drafting of a [NbS handbook](#), chaired the session focused on Nature-based Solutions, and provided technical support to participants in the development of their proposals. The program enabled participants to consult and analyze the SECAPs of their municipalities, propose concrete actions, and actively support the implementation of local climate plans (Phase 1).

In Phase 2, teachers shared the course content with their students, and some have already progressed to Phase 3, initiating discussions with their municipal administrations. Notably,

three classes – totalling 54 students – have already submitted requests to their mayors, urging their municipalities to develop their own SECAPs.

Finally, the upcoming Finance Innovation Festival, organized by the NATURANCE project in Brussels on 3–5 February, will include the award ceremony and the final Naturethon event **“Seeds of Change: Citizens & Cities”** – a speed-dating session showcasing 9 ongoing projects aimed at engaging citizens in the deployment of urban Nature-based Solutions. More details are available [on the project's website](#).